

HIGHER EDUCATION, HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT AND INDONESIAN NATIONAL ARMY (TNI-AD) SOLDIER EDUCATION IN INDONESIA: LESSONS FROM *SEKOLAH MILITER STAF DAN KOMANDO ANGKATAN DARAT* (SESKOAD)

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Abstrak

This research analyzes the challenges of higher education for Indonesian National Army (TNI-AD) soldiers in *Sekolah Militer Sekolah Staf dan Komando Angkatan Darat* (SESKOAD) which is the highest general development educational institution for the Indonesian Army, which was established to provide the knowledge and abilities of TNI-AD officers to become TNI leaders. This research method is qualitative-analytical regarding the challenges of higher education for TNI-AD soldiers in SESKOAD. The findings of this research show that the current lecturers are qualified and can carry out their duties even though they are not yet ideal from a general education point of view. Lecturer qualifications need to be improved in terms of placement and recruitment of lecturers. Currently all mid-level officers from the aspect of transfers and shifts in position are based on the decision of the Chief of Army Staff as personnel supervisor. The contribution of this research can be a reference in managing the quality of teaching staff in encouraging the quality of higher education in SESKOAD.

Kata Kunci: Lecturer Qualifications, Assignments and Higher Education, TNI-AD, SESKOAD.

INTRODUCTION

Human resource managers are challenged to meet the demands of an ever-increasing technology-driven environment (Daft, R. L., 2010; Dessler, G., 1997; Ferdinand Drucker, P., 2007).

Educational institutions are also challenged to keep up with changes in the global business environment as well as increasing demands for accountability from stakeholders (Brewer, P. D., & Brewer, K. L., 2010; Jackson, S. E. & Schuler, R. S., 1990; Kochan, T. A., Smith, M., et al., 1994).

Human resource management (HRM) activities, and the objectives of university business programs can result in a better understanding of how to prepare graduates to take on roles in the business environment as well as provide university programs with a good way to measure

the quality assurance of learning (Daft, R. L., 2010; Dessler, G., 1997; Ferdinand Drucker, P., 2007; Taylor, T. et al., 2015).

The aim of this study is to analyze the challenges of higher education for TNI-AD soldiers at the Army Staff and Command School (SESKOAD) military school which is the highest general development educational institution of the Army which was established to provide knowledge and skills for TNI-AD officers to become TNI leaders.

SESKOAD as an educational institution within the Indonesian Army and its ability to respond to curriculum demands will be greatly influenced by the presence of lecturers who are not only qualified and professional but also have competency standards that refer to the national and military education system so that they can meet the demands of student officer graduates' abilities.

Who are ready to be used on assignments and create SESKOAD graduates who have a degree/qualification (S-2) in applied land military operations (Rachman, A., 2020; Widodo, A. C., 2022; Suhandi, C. et al., 2019).

Since 1951, this TNI-AD educational institution was initially called SSKAD which was established through Kasad Decree Number: 44/KSAD/KPTS/51 concerning the Establishment of the Army Education Planning Commission, and in 1961 it changed its name to the TNI-AD Command and Staff College. SESKOAD in educating Middle Officers from the TNI-AD, TNI-AU, TNI-AL, Indonesian National Police and students representing friendly countries.

Mid-level officers are trained to become leaders in the future based on the experience and knowledge of the teaching staff at SESKOAD so that the output of the SESKOAD program can be TNI officers who are capable of military strategy and analysis (Buttler, J. et al., 1991; Hall, AO, & Fu, MC., 2015; Rachman, A., 2020; Widodo, A. C., 2022; Suhandi, C. et al., 2019).

Previous research tends to look at the potential of the Army Command and Staff College (SESKOAD) which focuses more on opportunities and strengths, as stated by Rachman, A. (2020) that SESKOAD as an educational institution does not only play a role in the Army and National Armed Forces, but played a role in developing nationalist doctrine and love of the country as a soldier in the Indonesian Army and spread the expansion of the role of education. Research from Widodo, A. C. (2022) states that SESKOAD provides education based on the demands and needs of the times.

Such as implementing education during the Covid-19 pandemic by revising the appropriate education curriculum, increasing the capabilities of officers at SESKOAD, improving technology-based education facilities, expanding website capacity and increasing the ability of lecturers in the teaching and learning process.

Research from Suhandi, C. et al. (2019) states that:

- 1) The role of SESKOAD in preparing TNI-AD officers to become TNI leaders in the era of globalization must be adjusted to providing material on developments in the international and national strategic environment;
- 2) Things that influence the role of SESKOAD in preparing TNI-AD officers to be ready to become leaders in the era of globalization include lecture material, the quality of lecturers and developing insight through comparative studies and field work lectures. Therefore, the challenges at the Army Staff and Command School (SESKOAD) are still not widely discussed by previous research which more or less influence the quality of educational provision at the SESKOAD for TNI-AD officers/soldiers. This research focuses on exploring the challenges of the quality of human resources for teaching staff in organizing and managing education at the Army Command and Staff College (SESKOAD).

In encouraging the improvement of human resources and the qualifications of lecturers at SESKOAD which has not been effective due to various obstacles such as the replacement of existing lecturer personnel determined by the Army Chief of Staff (Kasad), the qualifications of teaching staff are not yet ideal because they are not in accordance with what is required in scope of special capabilities according to Army Chief of Staff regulations.

This research aims to analyze the challenges of higher education for TNI-AD soldiers at the SESKOAD. The focus of this research is to analyze the qualifications of lecturers at the SESKOAD as a challenge in improving the quality of learning in higher education. Human resources, especially current lecturers, still need to be improved from the aspect of general education, because they are faced with the development of the globalization era and the education of current students for the next three years is generally better than the current teaching staff at SESKOAD.

RESEARCH METHOD

Research Design

In this research, the authors used a qualitative method, with a strategy of interviewing informants and case studies so that the facts could be obtained through a question and answer process and observation of the teaching and learning process and the planning of lecturers who were at SESKOAD or who were going to become lecturers. This strategy was chosen because it is in accordance with the objectives of this research, namely the qualifications of lecturers at the SESKOAD military school.

According to Creswell (2010), descriptive research is defined as research carried out to determine the value of independent variables, either one or more variables (independent) without making comparisons, or connecting one variable with another variable, so it can be judged that the descriptive qualitative method aims to explain the problem in detail and in more depth.

This research uses the concept of human resource management (HRM) (Brewer, P. D., & Brewer, K. L., 2010) at university colleges to produce a better understanding of how to prepare graduates to take on roles in the work environment, organizations, and society as well as management. University programs in a good way to measure the quality assurance of learning and institutional development.

Data Collection Technique

This research conducted field observations by visiting the Army Command and Staff College (SESKOAD) and obtaining various field notes. This research also conducted direct interviews face to face with informants as policy makers at SESKOAD so that data on the results of educational evaluations and educational curricula could be obtained.

Data Analysis Technique

This study involves a data analysis process in the form of descriptive qualitative analysis and interactive analysis (Miles, M. B. et al., 2014), which includes research data collection, data identification, research data reduction related to the research topic, data verification, data presentation, and conclusion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SESKOAD provides adequate knowledge and skills to student officers (Pasis) so that when they graduate from education they have sufficient provisions to carry out their role as staff or leaders in their units in the future (Rachman, A., 2020; Widodo, A. C., 2022; Suhanda, C. et al., 2019).

SESKOAD also strives to develop the abilities of Student Officers in their behavioral attitudes as Sapta Marga soldiers and the Soldier's Oath, knowledge, and skills as leaders and military staff at the level of operational positions of class V/Lieutenant Col, potential for selected positions of class IV/Colonel, as well as strategic positions in Pati with character, includes knowledge and skills of war military operations (OMP) and non-war military operations (OMSP), strategic planning, analysis, assessment of developments in the strategic environment and physical conditions (Pákozdi, M., & Bárdos, G., 2022; Sadikovich, K. M. , 2022; Mallick, P. K., 2017; Taylor, T. et al., 2015).

According to Drost (2002), teachers are strategic assets who are required to continue to experience the process of increasing their knowledge and teaching skills (on going formation) and have the ability to see into the future. This can all be fulfilled if teachers try to improve their educational qualifications.

Currently, SESKOAD based on changes in the decision of the Chief of Army Staff number Kep/972a/X/2019 in supporting educational curriculum and operational activities is supported by teaching staff or lecturers who must have the following abilities:

- (1) General Ability. Have the ability to deliver subject matter both theoretical and practical in accordance with instructional goals and educational targets (Rachman, A., 2020; Widodo, A. C., 2022; Suhanda, C. et al., 2019). This ability is obtained through formal teacher education and experience on assignments as teaching staff; and
- (2) Special Abilities:
 - a. Attitude and Behavior Development. By organic/non-organic lecturers who have experience in positions and assignments in aspects of struggle and leadership;
 - b. The knowledge and skills material which constitutes the core provision is provided by teaching staff who meet the following requirements:
 - 1) Military with the rank of Colonel/Lieutenant Colonel who graduated from Lemhannas, *Sesko TNI* or *Sesko Angkatan*;
 - 2) Have a Master's or Doctoral Degree academic qualification, special skills education and quality joint operations courses (Susopsgab), an expert in the fields of Science and Technology, Information Technology (IT) or other special skills required; and
 - 3) Have experience working as a lecturer who has the abilities and qualities in accordance with the military disciplines and supporting scientific knowledge they possess.

Lecturer

Lecturers are professional educators and scientists with the main task of teaching, transforming, developing and disseminating science, technology and art through education, research, and community service. Lecturers are required to have academic qualifications, competencies, educational certificates, be physically and mentally healthy, and meet other qualifications required by the university where they work, and have the ability to realize national education goals.

Table 1: Lecturers by Rank

No	Rank	Senior	Intermediate	Junior
1	Colonel	18	31	
2	Doctor	-		
3	S 2	6	12	
4	S 1	5	11	
5	High School	7	8	
6	Lieutenant Colonel			12
7	Doctor	-		
8	S2			3
9	S1			5
10	High School			4

Source. Periodic report to the Chief of Staff of the Army for the year 2022

The assignment of Indonesian Army officers as instructors is only within the educational institution of the Army Command and General Staff College (SESKOAD) (Decree of the Chief of Staff of the Army Number KEP/686/IX/2015 regarding technical guidelines for educational

personnel). Instructors serve as educators entrusted with the task of delivering branches of universal knowledge or knowledge related to national defense to officer students at SESKOAD, based on their level of knowledge or expertise.

Lecturers are required to have academic qualifications, competencies, teaching certificates, physical and spiritual health, and meet other qualifications stipulated by the higher education institution where they are assigned, as well as possess the ability to achieve the goals of national education (Article 45 of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 14 of 2005 concerning teachers and lecturers).

Additionally, in accordance with Article 46 of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 14 of 2005 concerning teachers and lecturers, they must have the following minimum academic qualifications:

- (a) Graduates of master's programs for diploma or bachelor's programs; and
- (b) Graduates of doctoral programs for postgraduate programs.

According to Schuler, R.S. and Walker, J.W. (1990), creativity is the ability to think divergently (spread out, not in one direction) to explore various alternative answers to a problem that is equally valid. Guilford's definition provides an understanding that creativity is the ability to choose in thinking. Every problem actually opens up many choices.

There are various options available, each with its own advantages and disadvantages. If, according to the assessment, one option is deemed less appropriate, the mind will automatically leap to other alternatives that are possible in human thinking. According to Spencer, M. Lyle & Spencer, M. Signe (1993), they then formulated the meaning of creativity as a person's ability to create new combinations. Creativity depends heavily on an individual's creative thinking, which is the process of creating new ideas.

The provision of education to the military may be one of the strongest reasons individuals choose to join the military rather than the civilian workforce. For instance, research indicates that the ability to advance one's education at an accredited institution while pursuing professional military education is a unique incentive that consistently helps the Air Force meet its recruitment goals compared to other branches (Pluviose, 2007).

Additionally, in general education, Grade Point Average (GPA) is known as a significant predictor of college academic performance and persistence (Allen et al., 2008; Hoffman & Lowitzi, 2005; Stewart et al., 2015; Witkow et al., 2015; Zheng et al., 2002). Similar credentials can be attained through civilian institutions, and degree requirements are equivalent to similar programs in civilian institutions (Adamo & Connolly, 1977; Richardson, 1977).

Throughout a military career, soldiers are required to attain advanced levels of professional military education. The branch of service, rank, career specialization, and current government needs all influence the required level of education (Gleiman & Zacharakis, 2016). While the military encourages service members to enroll in higher education, they report that it is a secondary priority to their military duties (Starr-Glass, 2011).

Efforts to facilitate this integration become more challenging due to the perception that higher education is an "anti-military" institution (Briggs, 2012). Lack of understanding of military culture, referred to as the "military-civilian gap," coupled with media headlines heavily focused on post-traumatic stress disorder (Hayes, 2012), makes the endeavor more complex. Specific competencies of instructors with specialized subjects allow for the identification of essential features of a competent instructor in higher military education.

This presents an opportunity to develop a professional description as a complex systemic set of professional and personal qualities for specialized subject instructors (Ybchuk, 2019). The profession of an academic lecturer is associated with stress and a sense of control as an intentional causative influence. The adopted styles for coping with challenging stress situations and the belief in controlling one's actions are vital aspects of the teaching staff's job functions in military universities.

Their potential dependencies may provide additional insights needed to optimize the teaching process in higher education (Laskowski, 2019; Wright, P. M. & McMahan, G. C., 1992).

The qualifications for the position of educational personnel in the Indonesian Army (TNI-AD) regarding their placement in the functional position hierarchy of educational institutions are determined based on the respective qualifications. These qualifications include rank, minimum education, and assignment experience. In the event that an educational personnel is assessed to have the capabilities of one level higher, they can be placed at that level with the condition of obtaining priority for rank promotion. For SESKOAD, lecturers are categorized as follows:

1. Senior Lecturer (Dosen Utama):
 - a. Rank: Colonel.
 - b. Education: Prioritize Sesko TNI or equivalent.
 - c. Assignment Experience: Operational/Training/Staff/Research.
 - d. General Education: Preferably Master's degree (S-2).
2. Intermediate Lecturer (Dosen Madya).
 - a. Rank: Colonel.
 - b. Education: Minimum SESKOAD or equivalent.
 - c. Assignment Experience: Operational/Training/Staff/Research.
 - d. General Education: Preferably Master's degree (S-2).
3. Junior Lecturer (Dosen Muda).
 - a. Rank: Lieutenant Colonel.
 - b. Education: Minimum SESKOAD or equivalent.
 - c. Assignment Experience: Operational Unit/Training/Staff/Research.
 - d. General Education: Preferably Master's degree (S-2).

Preparation and planning is organized using all reasoning abilities for an action that will be taken to achieve goals. Planning is an essential process in the management of educational institutions. It encompasses a wide, complex range and requires considerable time. The core of planning involves formulating goals and coordinating the methods to achieve them. Planning has two significant meanings: first and foremost, it serves as the foundation (starting point) of the entire management process, and second, it directs all activities within the organization.

According to Mondy and Premeaux (1995), planning is the process of determining what should be achieved and how to make it a reality. Furthermore, Fred (2004) states that planning is crucial for the implementation and successful evaluation of strategies, especially because organizational activities such as organizing, motivating, staffing, and controlling depend on good planning.

In Law Number 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers, it is mentioned that a teacher is a professional educator with the main duty of educating, teaching, guiding, directing, training, assessing, and evaluating students. Meanwhile, a Lecturer is a professional educator and scientist with the main duty of transforming, developing, and disseminating knowledge, technology, and the arts through education, research, and community service.

In Article 8 of Law Number 14 of 2005, it is explained that a teacher is required to have academic qualifications obtained through higher education, either in a bachelor's program or an applied bachelor's program. A teacher is also obliged to have competencies, including pedagogical, personality, social, and professional competencies acquired through professional education. They must also possess an educator certificate organized by a university that has an accredited education personnel procurement program and designated by the government as proof that the teacher has met the requirements.

Similarly to teachers, lecturers are also required to have academic qualifications, competencies, and educator certificates. However, unlike teachers, the minimum academic qualification for a lecturer is not a bachelor's or applied bachelor's degree but a graduate of a master's program for a diploma or bachelor's program and a graduate of a doctoral program for a postgraduate program.

Realizing the importance of having qualified and professional lecturers, the need for lecturers with competencies is essential to prepare future leaders of the Indonesian Army who can prevent and face various threats that the nation may encounter in the future.

Peter F. Drucker, a writer often referred to as the "father of modern management," once said in his book "People and Performance" (Ferdinand Drucker 2007) that managing an organization in the era of globalization requires not only experience but also competence. Competence, in this context, can be interpreted as the ability to master academic knowledge and skills to support professional duties. Thus, human resources managing organizations are always prepared to face various challenges and threats that arise at any moment. Based on an interview with the Head of the Corps of Lecturers at SESKOAD, the Head mentioned to the writer that:

“The lecturers currently present at SESKOAD have not all undergone military teacher education, and not all have completed postgraduate education (S2). However, due to organizational needs and the rank progression that must be followed, the current lecturers do not yet fully align with expectations, both in terms of teaching experience and the educational levels they have attained.”

The profession of a lecturer is a specialized job carried out based on certain principles. In Article 7, paragraph (1) of Law Number 14 of 2005, it is stated that lecturers must have a commitment to continually improve the quality of education, faith, piety, and noble character.

Furthermore, Article 45 of Law Number 14 of 2005 specifies that lecturers are required to have academic qualifications, educational background, competencies, and certifications required for their duties. Additionally, Article 60 of Law Number 14 of 2005 outlines the obligations of lecturers as professionals, one of which is to continuously enhance and develop academic qualifications and competencies in line with the progress of science, technology, and the arts. From the explanations in Law Number 14 of 2005, it is evident that lecturers play a crucial role in the development of education, research, and knowledge on a broad scale.

As the highest education institution in the army, SESKOAD needs to pay attention to the qualifications and competencies of lecturers as educators. This involves ensuring the right number of lecturers with appropriate qualifications and competencies.

Through proper job planning and analysis, SESKOAD can establish standards for the qualifications and competencies of officers who will serve as lecturers. This includes standardizing knowledge, skills, abilities, competencies, qualifications, and characteristics, both in military and non-military sciences. The goal is to enable SESKOAD to place human resources with the qualifications and competencies of individuals in the right positions (Right Man on the Right Place).

With proper planning, SESKOAD can also combine the standards of the Indonesian National Military (TNI) with the standards of the national education system and the standards for teachers/lecturers outlined in Law Number 20 of 2003 and Law Number 14 of 2005 for lecturers and military instructors. This also includes Regulations of the Head of the National Administration Institute Number 5 and 6 of 2008 for instructors.

In this combination, military rank, military education, and operational experience are integrated with academic qualifications and psychological competencies. This results in a harmonious blend between public administration commonly applied to civilian institutions and military administration specialized for the TNI as the military institution in Indonesia.

Improving the standards of competence and qualifications for lecturers at SESKOAD is one way to enhance the quality of graduates. Of course, raising the standards of competence and educational qualifications at SESKOAD requires accurate planning, considering the appropriate processes.

The goal is nothing less than achieving SESKOAD's vision of creating the best, honorable, and respected future leaders for the Indonesian Army (TNI-AD), TNI, and the nation. SESKOAD also aims to produce graduates with character, professionalism, resilience, integrity, capable of applying knowledge in social, technological, managerial, strategic, territorial, operational, martial arts, and able to maintain physical and fitness standards.

By carefully considering the availability of competent and qualified lecturers and recognizing the importance of human resource planning, SESKOAD currently needs an improved management and administrative pattern in human resource planning. This is crucial to meet the requirements for lecturer qualifications and competencies, ensuring that SESKOAD becomes more quality-oriented and professional.

The quality of SESKOAD as an educational institution within the Indonesian Army (TNI-AD) and its ability to respond to future challenges with an operational curriculum will be greatly influenced by the presence of lecturers who, in addition to being of high quality, are also grounded in professionalism. However, this should be done while maintaining standards that align with the national education system.

This is essential to meet the demands of the SESKOAD education curriculum, which aims to develop the capabilities of its graduates in the field of military professionalism and leads towards the achievement of postgraduate qualifications (S-2). Therefore, the need for competent lecturers is imperative and cannot be delayed any longer.

Recognizing the importance of having qualified, professional, and competent lecturers in the regular education programs at SESKOAD to meet the demands of SESKOAD's curriculum, there is a need for a concept regarding the formulation of competencies and qualifications required by lecturers serving at SESKOAD.

The level of mastery, for example, should be 100% or may be less than 100%. In line with these principles, the issue of learning materials plays a crucial role in helping participants (Pasis) achieve competency standards. The learning materials present in the SESKOAD education curriculum (Kurdik) can be effectively delivered to students only if presented by lecturers who possess the expected competencies. Thus, it can be ensured that with competent and qualified lecturers, the institution will be able to meet the demands of the established education curriculum. To ensure that lecturers in the TNI-AD have high motivation and enthusiasm, it is necessary to consider creating a separate career ladder for educators.

According to Chauhan & Sharma (2015: 80), the concept of teacher education is well-known, stating that the quality and level of student achievement are primarily determined by teacher competence, sensitivity, and motivation. Teacher competence includes pedagogical competence, personality competence, social competence, and professional competence. So far, SESKOAD has only been conducting data collection on the quantity, quality, and qualifications of lecturers to subsequently make proposals to the higher authorities. With human resource planning and job analysis, SESKOAD can provide better recommendations compared to not having these processes in place. Through accurate human resource planning and job analysis, SESKOAD can establish a standard qualification and competency framework for officers who

will serve as lecturers in the SESKOAD environment. This includes standardizing knowledge, skills, abilities, competencies, qualifications, and characteristics, both in military and non-military subjects. The goal is to ensure that SESKOAD can place human resources with the qualifications and competencies of individuals in the right positions (Right Man on the Right Place). According to Beven (2009), an educational instructor must be competent in designing learning experiences rich in imparting knowledge to students through mastery of pedagogical principles and the curriculum of vocational education.

“Interview results with the Corps of Cadets Commander state that those suitable to become educators at SESKOAD are:

- (a) Have undergone military teacher education;*
- (b) Have completed at least a Master's degree education; and*
- (c) Have attended Sesko TNI (Military Staff College).”*

The implementation to enhance the academic capabilities of lecturers involves increasing scholarship opportunities for lecturers to pursue both civilian and military education.

Based on the above understanding, it can be concluded that skills are abilities acquired through formal learning and training in educational institutions, enabling them to provide lessons to officer students effectively.

Pertaining to Assignments/Duties

Duties are specific activities carried out in an organization, according to John & Mary Miner in Moekijat (1998:10), stating that a task is a specific work activity performed for a particular purpose. Wiltshire (2016) defines work as a dynamic concept with various synonyms and definitions, namely

- (1) Work refers to the importance of a specific activity, time, and energy spent.
- (2) Work is a series of specific skills and competencies that must be constantly improved over time.
- (3) Work is a way to maintain a position rather than just earning a living.

In the military context, assignments have a different meaning, representing a commitment to serve the nation and the people while emphasizing loyalty. Employee loyalty (usually synonymous with commitment) to the organization is sometimes seen as an attitude (Meyer and Allen, 1991). Loyalty is seen as an employee's feeling attached to an organization (Buchanan, 2015), but not an attitude (or thinking component) that is important in the organization, but rather a bottom-line action component (Hoskins, 2012). Military officers are continuously instilled with critical leadership traits for their operational careers. They are also taught that leadership skills enable them, with sufficient training, to perform any job. George Reed, a former career Army officer and a professor who transitioned to civilian academia, wrote in 2011 that the main problem with military faculty personnel arises from the fact that colleges have little control over who serves there as military faculty members.

The personnel system seems to believe that any old colonel can do it, but many examples suggest otherwise. Assignments are made for a number of reasons unrelated to someone's ability or even interest in teaching. I remember one very distressing case where the Air Force sent an officer to teach at the Army War College who suffered from a noticeable speech disorder. For educational purposes and intellectual agility, education faculty members must be allowed to pursue meaningful assignments to attract high-value students. Johnson-Freese (2012). Military manpower is diverse and encompasses various socio-economic strata (Hassan et al., 2010). The rapid and technical training provided by the military instills discipline and strong teamwork in its members while offering them various opportunities to apply their skills in real-world situations (DiRamio & Jarvis, 2011). Reintegration into civilian communities after military service can be a challenging time for veterans. To support their transition, colleges and universities need to provide diverse assistance resources. Although campus-based services for veterans mostly focus on educational benefits, strategies that enhance awareness of the layered and complex experiences surrounding military service are needed (Osborne, 2013). The appointment of a lecturer at SESKOAD involves diverse assignments. In addition to necessitating lecturers with educational backgrounds relevant to the subjects taught to officer students, SESKOAD, being a professional military education institution, also demands lecturers with field assignment experience that complements the teaching process.

The assignment experience contributes to enriching insights and deepening the expertise of lecturers in the teaching process, especially for subjects with specific applied skills. To become a lecturer, experience in positions within the TNI-AD units is essential. Without this, it would be challenging to find qualified lecturers, and recognition of this experience is an integral part of the lecturer's competence-building process. Therefore, potential officers who aim to become lecturers need to record data regarding various assignments aligned with the career direction of becoming a lecturer at SESKOAD. The starting point to generate skilled and reliable human resources requires planning. Success in providing the workforce depends on accuracy in employee placement, both for new and existing employees in new positions. According to Mathis, Robert L., and John H. Jackson (2001), placement is the activity of placing someone in a suitable job position because it can affect the quality and quantity of work.

There are several working principles to consider in employee placement. Here are these principles:

1. **Direction-Related Principle:** Employees will be asked to focus on the goals to be achieved.
2. **Unity of Command Principle:** A principle that keeps employees always under the influence of the given command. This makes employees have only one superior.
3. **Work Productivity and Efficiency Principle:** The key to the company's goals as work productivity and efficiency must be achieved for the company's objectives.
4. **Humanity Principle:** A principle that sees humans as workers who must be respected in their position and treated as worthy human beings.

5. Democracy Principle: A principle showing an attitude of mutual respect and appreciation in carrying out activities related to work.
6. The Right Man On The Right Place Principle: A principle that must be implemented in the placement process. This principle places workers in positions that match their abilities.
7. Equal Pay for Equal Work Principle: A principle of providing appropriate wages based on the work performance of employees.
8. Unity of Direction Principle: A principle that must be applied by the company to each employee so that they can carry out tasks in line with the plans and programs that have been made.

According to Hasibuan, Malayu S.P. (2003), placement is defined as placing someone in the right job position, and how well an employee fits their job will affect the quantity and quality of work. Furthermore, Praskova Creed and Hood (2015) explain that placement planning should start with observing the extent of experience and education possessed by an employee. Thus, it will be easier to observe the career path of the employee. From the above understanding, job placement is an effort to channel the abilities of employees optimally by placing them in positions or roles that are most suitable for job satisfaction and optimal performance. The Administrative Guidelines on Officer Career Development were approved by the Chief of Staff of the Army with Decree No. Skep/441/XI/2006 dated November 20, 2006, containing:

- (1) Principles in the implementation of officer career development activities, as follows:
 - (a) Proper officer placement in the right position is done through accurate classification;
 - (b) Enhancing the capabilities, skills, interests, and talents of officers through assignments, education, and training suitable for their potential; and
 - (c) Providing a fair opportunity for each officer to develop their career through good planning and a rotation of assignments and educational opportunities for progress; and
- (2) Officer assignments in a position are a form of leadership trust in an officer, resulting in responsibility for the individual. Therefore, placement in a position must be able to develop the potential of the individual to a higher position and be tailored to their abilities.

In the context of position placement. Currently, the parameters or indicators used by the TNI-AD Personnel Staff in assigning officer positions include:

Table 2: Job Placement Assessment

Talent Scouting.	Assessment Criteria for the Position of Commander	Psychology.	List of Assessments.	Track Record.	Sociometry.
<p>The talent scouting used by the TNI-AD (Indonesian Army) currently includes various assessment aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Dikma (Military Academy Graduation), b. Dikbangum (Combat Training), c. Dikbangpes typology of the area/unit assignment, d. Operational assignments, e. Psychological qualifications, f. Length of service, g. Daftar penilaian (Assessment List), h. Kotama assignments, i. MDP (Military Development Program), j. Overseas assignments and achievements. 	<p>The competence assessment for the position of Commander in the Army involves a selection process covering the following subjects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Academic, b. Psychology, c. Physical fitness 	<p>This is one of the methods used by the Army Personnel Staff in placing an officer in a position, focusing on the psychological aspects by observing an individual's interests and talents, with the expectation that the officer can occupy a position in line with their qualifications and psychological classification.</p>	<p>The assessment list is used as one of the requirements for promotion and rank increase, currently using assessments from the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Personality, b. Competence, c. Health, d. Physical fitness, e. Family life, f. Potential possessed by an officer. <p>The assessment is conducted periodically or when proposing education and promotion.</p>	<p>Track record is used in directing the position of an officer by observing their life history. The elements observed include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Job history b. Operational assignments c. Education d. Rank promotions e. Specific achievement records, if any. f. Curriculum Vitae 	<p>Sociometry is currently used as a parameter to measure the level of acceptability of an officer by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Superior officers, b. Colleagues, c. Subordinate officers in the TNI-AD environment, as considerations for promotion within the TNI-AD.

Source: Decree of the Army Chief of Staff No. Skep/441/XI/2006 dated November 20, 2006.

Observing the table above, the placement of positions in the structure of the TNI-AD requires a lengthy career journey with ever-changing and varied dynamics, demanding a high level of consistency. Considering the Army Chief's regulations associated with service experience, it is one of the factors that influence lecturers in delivering military and general education to achieve the vision and mission of education at SESKOAD.

Higher Education

Education is a conscious and planned effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning processes so that learners actively develop their potential to possess spiritual and religious strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and skills needed for themselves, society, nation, and state. Based on the Republic of Indonesia Law number 12 of 2012 concerning higher education, Higher Education is an educational level after secondary education that includes diploma programs, undergraduate programs, master's programs, doctoral programs, and professional programs, as well as specialist programs, organized by higher education institutions based on the culture of the Indonesian nation.

The chosen level of education will influence the behavior of educators, so Higher Education functions to:

- (a) Develop the abilities and shape the character and civilization of the nation in order to enlighten the nation's life;
- (b) Develop an innovative, responsive, creative, competitive, and cooperative Academic Community through the implementation of the Tri Dharma; and
- (c) Develop Science and Technology by considering and applying Humanitarian values.

In the educational context, an individual is currently considered something significant, but according to the Republic of Indonesia Law number 12 of 2012 concerning higher education, Higher Education aims to:

- (a) Develop the potential of students to become individuals who are faithful and devoted to the Almighty, with noble character, health, knowledgeable, skilled, creative, independent, competent, and cultured for the nation's interests;
- (b) Produce graduates who master branches of Science and/or Technology to meet national needs and increase the nation's competitiveness;
- (c) Produce Science and Technology through Research that considers and applies Humanitarian values to be beneficial for the progress of the nation, as well as the progress of civilization and the well-being of humanity; and
- (d) Realize Community Service based on reasoning and Research that is beneficial in advancing public welfare and enlightening the nation's life.

Meanwhile, SESKOAD, as the highest general education institution in the Army, needs to have appropriate human resource planning, especially for educational positions such as lecturers and trainers who provide education, teaching, and guidance to officer students at SESKOAD. They

need to have high education qualifications so that the teaching and learning process can be carried out effectively as expected.

Table 3: Level of Education of the Lecturers at the SESKOAD

No		2021	2022
1	Doctor	-	-
2	S 2	11	21
3	S 1	19	21
4	High School	28	19

Source: SESKOAD Annual Reports for 2021 and 2022

The table above shows the general education of lecturers at SESKOAD, which still varies but has seen an increase in the number who have undergone general education. Therefore, SESKOAD needs to be consistent in planning the educational needs of educators, especially for positions like lecturers and instructors who provide education, teaching, and guidance to officer students at SESKOAD. The Chief of Staff of the Army, as the decision-maker in the Army's position placements, also plays a role in this.

The competence of lecturers in terms of expertise, personality, professionalism, and social aspects that must be possessed by an educator is also a consideration for SESKOAD in positioning someone in a lecturer position. Because competence in the military field alone is not enough to provide good and optimal education to the Dikreg Participants at SESKOAD. Lecturers at SESKOAD need to have the ability to manage learning for participants, including developing curriculum, lesson planning, implementing learning, utilizing learning technology, and conducting learning assessments to maximize participant potential. In addition, lecturers at SESKOAD are also required to master teaching materials and teaching methods to ensure that the education process runs optimally. Of course, acquiring these abilities is not easy. It

requires commitment from both lecturers and SESKOAD as an educational institution to acquire and develop these abilities.

The higher education or general education of a military lecturer can be developed through the development of communicative competence. Communicative competence in a foreign language refers to learning to use communicative strategies and mechanisms needed to provide efficient interaction (Nikolaeva, 2011). Furthermore, communicative competence in a foreign language includes knowledge of communication in different situations with different communicants, as well as the basics of verbal and nonverbal interaction, the ability to use them efficiently in specific communication as a sender and receiver (Batsevych, 2009). The development of communicative competence in a foreign language by military university lecturers allows for the application of andragogy models in the educational process (Aristarkhova, 2021).

The preparation of educators at SESKOAD is based on the Decree of the Chief of Staff of the Army Number Keputusan/866/IX/2015 dated September 18, 2015, regarding technical instructions for educators.

Table 3: Policies for Preparing Educators in the TNI-AD

MABESAD	SESKOAD
<p>Chief of Staff of the Army:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Determines general policies for the development and utilization of educators required by educational institutions within the TNI-AD. 2. Determines and supports budgetary needs for the procurement of supporting tools for the development and utilization of educators required by educational institutions within the TNI-AD. 	<p>Commander of SESKOAD:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establishes policies, guidelines, and broad outlines of plans and proposes programs for the development and utilization of educators in SESKOAD. 2. Controls assistance, supervision, development, and utilization of educators that are the responsibility of SESKOAD. 3. Is responsible for the execution of duties to the Chief of Staff of the Army.
<p>Assistant for Personnel Affairs to the Chief of Staff of the Army:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Implements proposals for the needs of programs for the development and utilization of educators in educational institutions within the TNI-AD. 2. Prepares personnel for educators according to the needs of educational institutions to support educational operations. 3. Carries out supervision and control over the implementation of the development and utilization of educators in educational institutions within the TNI-AD. 4. Is responsible for the execution of duties to the Chief of Staff of the Army. 	<p>Director of Education and Training (Dirbindik) SESKOAD:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Implements development, assistance, utilization, supervision, and control of the development of educators in SESKOAD. 2. Plans and proposes programs and budgetary needs for the procurement of supporting tools for the development and utilization of educators required by SESKOAD. 3. Gathers data and proposes the fulfillment of shortages of educators and improvements in their welfare. 4. Is responsible for the execution of duties to the Commander of SESKOAD.

This policy regulates the provisions regarding the duties and responsibilities of the Chief of Staff of the Army, the Commander of SESKOAD, and the Educators in preparing educators, particularly lecturers, to carry out their main duties as educators and to prepare themselves both

in terms of general knowledge acquired from educational institutions/universities and military knowledge obtained from training, courses, and advanced education.

Looking at the data and theories above, the author sees that the role of the Chief of Staff of the Army and the Commander of SESKOAD is crucial in planning the availability of lecturers and improving the competence and qualifications of existing and future lecturers. The educational level of lecturers can significantly impact the teaching and learning process in terms of mastery of material, creativity, and the ability to provide solutions in the field of duty for future officer students.

Benefits of Lecturer Qualifications

In order to enhance the qualifications of lecturers, SESKOAD has collaborated with several universities to improve the capabilities and qualifications of its lecturers, ensuring they do not lag behind the educational qualifications of officer students and the new curriculum, where SESKOAD graduates will obtain a Master's degree (applied) in land military operations. In an interview with the Commander of SESKOAD, he stated:

“A strategic and continuous planning by SESKOAD and the Army Headquarters is necessary to prepare competent educators. Currently, SESKOAD has collaborated with the University of Defense (Unhan) and Unjani to involve educators at SESKOAD in education, both at the S1 and S2 levels up to S3. Coordination has also been carried out with the Headquarters of the Indonesian National Army to ensure that officers placed in SESKOAD preferably have a minimum of an S2 general education.”

Table 4: Comparison of SESKOAD Lecturer Qualifications with the United States and Australia

NO	SESKOAD
1	Military personnel with the rank of Colonel/Lieutenant Colonel who are graduates of the National Resilience Institute (Lemhannas), the Armed Forces Staff College (Sesko TNI), or the Army Staff College (Sesko Angkatan)
2	Required to have academic qualifications at the Master's (S-2) or Doctorate (S-3) level, specialized education, and quality in joint operational courses (Susopsgab). They should also be experts in the field of Ilpengtek (Information Technology) or other specific skills as required. emiliki kualifikasi akademis Strata S-2 maupun S-3, pendidikan kemampuan khusus dan kualitas kursus operasi gabungan (Susopsgab), Ahli bidang Ilpengtek, Teknologi Informasi (TI) ataupun keterampilan khusus lainnya yang diperlukan.
3	Experience as a lecturer is necessary, with capabilities and qualities aligned with their military discipline or supporting scientific disciplines.
SESKO AMERIKA	
1	Quality: Instructors (Gadik) consist of civilian employees (retired military or pure civilian) and active officers with the rank of Lieutenant Colonel and Colonel. The majority of instructors hold masters or doctoral degrees. Generally, all Gadik must understand and master the subjects they are responsible for. The requirements to become a Gadik include: a. Having a background in the subject matter they are responsible for and a minimum of a Master's degree (S2). b. Having operational experience in combat or peacekeeping operations within the Army, across services, and multinational environments.

2	Quantity: The number of educators providing lessons is around 120, comprising 60% civilians (a combination of retired military and pure civilians) and 40% active military officers.
AUSTRALIA	
1	ANU lecturers hold the qualifications of Professor, Doctor, or at least a Master's degree and are Subject Matter Experts (SME) in the given subject matter.
2	External lecturers and Senior Military Officers, both domestic and international, serve as SMEs in related subjects.
3	Directing Staff (DS) amount to 21 individuals from the Australian Defence Force (ADF) and Exchange DS from Indonesia, the United States, the United Kingdom, Canada, New Zealand, Fiji, and Malaysia.
4	Historians play a crucial role in various military campaigns and peacekeeping missions under the United Nations (UN) involving ADF personnel.
5	Officials in fields related to the subject matter provide detailed and comprehensive insights, such as in modules on Capability, ATF, and JOP.

The improvement of qualifications for instructors, as seen in the comparison table with instructors from other countries in SESKOAD, will have many benefits for SESKOAD in planning and creating a roadmap for the ideal competence and qualifications of instructors placed in SESKOAD, even though their placement may change in the future.

Human Resources Management activities in the military school, the Army Staff and Command School (SESKOAD), that need to be pursued include orientation, socialization, training, development, performance assessment, and enhancement of knowledge and skills for TNI-AD officers to become leaders in the TNI. Recognizing that the knowledge required by human resources to succeed in their careers within the organization requires a commitment to continuous learning, university curricula need to provide opportunities for students to acquire, explore, and apply factual, conceptual, procedural, and metacognitive knowledge that is advanced and profound, and then tools to add and enhance their knowledge dimensions after graduation.

CONCLUSION

The research results indicate that the qualification of instructors needs improvement in terms of placement and acceptance of current instructors, where all middle-ranking officers are subject to transfers and position shifts based on decisions from the Army Chief of Staff as the personnel supervisor. Despite input and suggestions from the SESKOAD education commander regarding the needs of teaching personnel, all policies cannot be separated from the organizational needs, especially those of the Army. Further results show that the qualification of instructors at SESKOAD requires special policies from the leadership of the Army to place professional instructors who, in addition to being competent in military science, also need to undergo general education to support their main tasks as educators with proficiency in various fields of knowledge.

Finally, human resources activities involving rewards, placements, succession planning, and termination of employment cause concerns for the organization in retaining and replacing knowledgeable workers. Designing a reward and compensation system that includes monetary and non-monetary rewards, tangible and intangible, as well as intrinsic and extrinsic rewards

is essential in maximizing the goals of development and administrative performance assessment systems to maintain and enhance employee knowledge. Tacit and explicit knowledge is targeted for examination, improvement, and recognition. Termination, placement, and succession planning HR activities require strategies to capture and retain knowledge stored in departing human resources. Managers need to be equipped with metacognitive knowledge that includes strategic knowledge, conditional and contextual knowledge about cognitive tasks, and self-knowledge to precisely address potential knowledge gaps—within the organization and within themselves. Therefore, military education programs at the Army Staff and Command School (SESKOAD) need to focus on human resource planning at SESKOAD that can proceed according to organizational needs, requiring the attention and leadership of the Army to place educators at SESKOAD.

Competing Interests

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

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